

Supplemental Methods for “Embedding Vehicle–Bridge Coupled Dynamics in Physics-Informed Neural Networks for Structural Response Prediction”

Supplemental Methods

S1. Road-roughness generation

The rough-surface simulations use a deterministic realization of an ISO-8608-type class-A road profile. The one-sided spatial power spectral density is

$$G_d(n) = \frac{a_r}{(2\pi n)^2}, \quad a_r = 2.0 \times 10^{-6} \text{ m}^3/\text{cycle}, \quad 0.05 \leq n \leq 1.0 \text{ cycle/m.} \quad (\text{S1})$$

The road is synthesized with $N_r = 20$ harmonic components. With

$$\Delta n = \frac{n_{\max} - n_{\min}}{N_r}, \quad n_m = n_{\min} + (m - 1)\Delta n, \quad m = 1, \dots, N_r, \quad (\text{S2})$$

the raw random-phase profile is

$$r_{\text{raw}}(x) = \sum_{m=1}^{N_r} \sqrt{2G_d(n_m)\Delta n} \cos(2\pi n_m x - \vartheta_m). \quad (\text{S3})$$

The phase vector $\{\vartheta_m\}_{m=1}^{N_r}$ is generated once using the deterministic seed 12345 and is reused without change in both the PINN residual evaluation and the Newmark– β reference solver. The final roughness profile is

$$r(x) = s_r W(x) r_{\text{raw}}(x), \quad s_r = 1.0, \quad (\text{S4})$$

where $W(x)$ is a half-cosine endpoint taper of length $\ell_w = 0.5$ m,

$$W(x) = \begin{cases} \frac{1}{2} [1 - \cos(\pi x/\ell_w)], & 0 < x < \ell_w, \\ 1, & \ell_w \leq x \leq L - \ell_w, \\ \frac{1}{2} [1 - \cos\{\pi(L - x)/\ell_w\}], & L - \ell_w < x < L, \\ 0, & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases} \quad (\text{S5})$$

The derivative used in the contact-velocity term includes both the raw-profile derivative and the taper derivative,

$$\frac{dr}{dx} = s_r \left(W'(x) r_{\text{raw}}(x) + W(x) \frac{dr_{\text{raw}}}{dx} \right), \quad \dot{r}[x_a(t)] = c \left. \frac{dr}{dx} \right|_{x=x_a(t)}. \quad (\text{S6})$$

Thus the same roughness displacement and roughness velocity are used in the PINN residual and in the direct coupled Newmark- β calculation. Figure S1 shows the displacement and velocity profiles used in the numerical examples.

Fig. S1: Prescribed roughness input used in the rough-surface VBI-PINN simulations.

S2. Network features and output scaling

The implemented PINN input vector is

$$\zeta(\tau, \kappa) = [\tau, \bar{\kappa}, \sqrt{\bar{\kappa}}, \gamma_M(\tau, \kappa), \gamma_F(\tau)]^T, \quad \bar{\kappa} = 2 \frac{\kappa - 0.8}{1.2 - 0.8} - 1. \quad (\text{S7})$$

The modal phase features are

$$\gamma_M = [\sin(\omega_{i0} T_0 \sqrt{\bar{\kappa}} \tau), \cos(\omega_{i0} T_0 \sqrt{\bar{\kappa}} \tau)]_{i=1}^{N_m}, \quad T_0 = L/c, \quad (\text{S8})$$

and the base temporal Fourier set is

$$\mathcal{F}_{\text{base}} = \{1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 8, 10, 12, 14, 16, 20\}. \quad (\text{S9})$$

For rough-surface simulations, additional Fourier frequencies are obtained from the spatial roughness frequencies. Each n_m gives the normalized-time frequency $n_m L$, and multiplication by the i -th bridge mode introduces the projected frequencies

$$n_m L, \quad n_m L + \frac{i}{2}, \quad \left| n_m L - \frac{i}{2} \right|, \quad i = 1, \dots, N_m. \quad (\text{S10})$$

Duplicate and non-positive frequencies are removed before forming

$$\gamma_F = [\sin(2\pi f \tau), \cos(2\pi f \tau)]_{f \in \mathcal{F}_{\text{base}} \cup \mathcal{F}_{\text{rough}}}. \quad (\text{S11})$$

The roughness displacement $r[x_a(t)]$ and velocity $c \, dr/dx|_{x=x_a(t)}$ are therefore evaluated inside the residual equations; they are not appended as pointwise neural-network input coordinates.

The network outputs are normalized before physical reconstruction. For the quarter-car model,

$$X_0 = \frac{M_v g}{K_v}, \quad Q_0 = \frac{F_0 L^3}{48EI_0}, \quad F_0 = M_v g, \quad (\text{S12})$$

where X_0 scales the vehicle displacement and Q_0 scales the bridge modal coordinates. For the half-car model,

$$Y_0 = \frac{F_0}{K_v}, \quad \Theta_0 = \frac{Y_0}{l_a}, \quad Q_0 = \frac{F_0 L^3}{48EI_0}, \quad F_0 = \frac{M_v g}{2}, \quad (\text{S13})$$

where Y_0 , Θ_0 , and Q_0 scale heave, pitch, and bridge modal coordinates, respectively. For the numerical half-car benchmark, $l_a = l_f = l_r = 2.0$ m.

S3. Residual normalization and temporal weighting

The raw residual magnitudes of the vehicle and bridge equations differ because they involve different masses, stiffnesses, and contact-force scales. The roughness-aware force scale is

$$F_{\text{rough,rms}} = \text{rms}_{x \in [0,L]} \left(K_v r(x) + C_v c \frac{dr}{dx}(x) \right), \quad F_{\text{res}} = F_0 + F_{\text{rough,rms}}, \quad A_{\text{res}} = \frac{F_{\text{res}}}{m_b}. \quad (\text{S14})$$

In the code, $F_{\text{rough,rms}}$ is computed from 4096 uniformly spaced points on the bridge. The quarter-car residual scale is F_{res} for the vehicle equation and A_{res} for each bridge modal equation. For the half-car model, the heave and pitch residual scales are F_{res} and $F_{\text{res}} l_a$, respectively, and the bridge modal residual scale remains A_{res} . The optimized pointwise objective uses $w_v = w_b = 1$ after this normalization.

The time-importance weights are deterministic and are applied only to contact-event regions. For the quarter-car model,

$$w_t(t) = 1 + w_e \exp \left[- \left(\frac{t - L/c}{\sigma_e} \right)^2 \right]. \quad (\text{S15})$$

For the half-car model,

$$w_t(t) = 1 + (w_{\text{tail}} - 1) \mathbf{1}_{L/c \leq t \leq (L+2l_a)/c} + w_e \sum_{t_e \in \{2l_a/c, L/c, (L+2l_a)/c\}} \exp \left[- \left(\frac{t - t_e}{\sigma_e} \right)^2 \right]. \quad (\text{S16})$$

The reported runs use $w_{\text{tail}} = 10$, $w_e = 5$, and $\sigma_e = 0.04$ s.

S4. Error metrics and computational-cost definitions

For a set of N bridge-displacement samples, the root-mean-square error is

$$\text{RMSE} = \sqrt{\frac{1}{N} \sum_{j=1}^N (u_{\Theta,j} - u_{\text{ref},j})^2}. \quad (\text{S17})$$

The peak- and range-normalized errors are

$$\text{NRMSE}_{\text{peak}} = \frac{\text{RMSE}}{\max_j |u_{\text{ref},j}|} \times 100\%, \quad \text{NRMSE}_{\text{range}} = \frac{\text{RMSE}}{\max_j u_{\text{ref},j} - \min_j u_{\text{ref},j}} \times 100\%. \quad (\text{S18})$$

For completeness, an additional RMS-normalized NRMSE can also be computed as

$$\text{NRMSE}_{\text{rms}} = \frac{\text{RMSE}}{\sqrt{N^{-1} \sum_{j=1}^N u_{\text{ref},j}^2}} \times 100\%. \quad (\text{S19})$$

This metric is provided as a supplementary diagnostic and is not used as the primary normalization in the main text. The maximum absolute error is $e_{\text{max}} = \max_j |u_{\Theta,j} - u_{\text{ref},j}|$. For parity plots, the scalar response is the maximum absolute mid-span deflection over time. Training time is reported as the complete offline optimization cost, including residual evaluation, automatic differentiation, backpropagation, optimizer updates, L-BFGS function evaluations, and checkpoint bookkeeping. PINN inference time is measured after training for full-field prediction over the specified stiffness grid. Newmark- β time is measured for the corresponding full stiffness sweep. Plotting, file input/output, and error-metric post-processing are excluded from the solver timing.

S5. Implementation details and computational cost

The numerical timing tests were performed using double precision on one NVIDIA H100 80 GB HBM3 GPU. Both stiffness-parametric surrogates used Class-A road roughness, three bridge modes, 61 stiffness values, and full-field reconstruction on 101 spatial points. The reported training time includes residual evaluation, automatic differentiation, backpropagation, optimizer updates, L-BFGS function evaluations, and checkpoint bookkeeping. PINN inference time is measured after training for full-field prediction over the complete 61-stiffness grid. Newmark- β time is measured for the corresponding direct coupled reference sweep with the same full-field reconstruction. Plotting, file input/output, and error-metric post-processing are excluded.

Table S1: Final decomposed loss components at the retained checkpoint.

Case	Total loss	L_v	L_b	L_{IC}
Quarter-car	2.55×10^{-5}	9.24×10^{-6}	1.62×10^{-5}	0
Half-car	7.49×10^{-5}	2.04×10^{-5}	5.04×10^{-5}	0

Table S2: Computational cost for the quarter-car VBI-PINN.

Quantity	Value	Notes
Case setup	549 time points; 61 stiffness cases	Class-A road, 3 bridge modes, 101 spatial points
Network size	283,396 parameters	7 hidden layers, width 192, tanh activation
Adam training	12,612.33 s (3.50 h)	80,000 Adam iterations
L-BFGS refinement	181.19 s (3.02 min)	After loading the best Adam checkpoint
Total PINN training	12,793.52 s (3.55 h)	Offline cost
PINN inference, all 61 cases	0.04432 s	Full-field prediction after training
PINN inference, mean per case	0.000727 s (0.727 ms)	Amortized online query time
Newmark- β sweep, all 61 cases	3.2021 s	Direct coupled reference sweep
Newmark- β mean per case	0.052493 s (52.49 ms)	Mean direct solver time
Online speedup after training	72.2 \times	Newmark sweep time divided by PINN inference time
Break-even repeated 61-case sweeps	4,051 sweeps	Approximate training-cost amortization point
Break-even single-stiffness queries	247,139 queries	Equivalent individual-query count

Table S3: Computational cost for the half-car VBI-PINN.

Quantity	Value	Notes
Case setup	629 time points; 61 stiffness cases	Class-A road, 3 bridge modes, 101 spatial points
Network size	283,589 parameters	7 hidden layers, width 192, tanh activation
Adam training	16,087.41 s (4.47 h)	80,000 Adam iterations
L-BFGS refinement	229.63 s (3.83 min)	After loading the best Adam checkpoint
Total PINN training	16,317.04 s (4.53 h)	Offline cost
PINN inference, all 61 cases	0.04547 s	Full-field prediction after training
PINN inference, mean per case	0.000745 s (0.745 ms)	Amortized online query time
Newmark- β sweep, all 61 cases	5.8575 s	Direct coupled reference sweep
Newmark- β mean per case	0.096025 s (96.02 ms)	Mean direct solver time
Online speedup after training	128.8 \times	Newmark sweep time divided by PINN inference time
Break-even repeated 61-case sweeps	2,807 sweeps	Approximate training-cost amortization point
Break-even single-stiffness queries	171,255 queries	Equivalent individual-query count